

Implications for the use of Distance Online Learning in Colleges of Media and Communication: Survey results

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Article Info	Abstract
<p data-bbox="197 490 368 521"><i>Article History</i></p> <p data-bbox="197 551 352 611">Received: May 06, 2021</p> <p data-bbox="197 645 384 705">Accepted: August 15, 2021</p> <hr/> <p data-bbox="197 734 328 766">Keywords :</p> <p data-bbox="197 768 464 918">Distance Online Learning, Media and Communication, Covid-19 pandemic, Arab region.</p> <p data-bbox="197 952 480 1012">DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5203287</p>	<p data-bbox="560 490 1401 1279"><i>In light of the sudden shift towards distance education called for by the global Covid-19 pandemic, questions are raised about the extent to which Arab universities are prepared for such a step in terms of infrastructure, the level of mastery of distance learning techniques among professors, and the implications of the Internet environment on the educational process. This paper presents the results of an opinion poll for Media and Communication professors in the Arab region conducted in June and July 2021. First, the level of information and communication technology (ICT) proficiency among the participants was addressed to measure their willingness to ensure online distance learning (DOL). Second, a special focus has been placed on potential technological factors to determine the most widely used DOL platforms. Third, the perception of Media and Communication professors participating in the survey about the implications of using DOL technologies was tracked to measure their effects on the educational operations. The findings show a good level of ICT proficiency, but with some differences in terms of the technical tools exploited, depending on the geographical area; the Zoom platform is the most used in the Arab region, mainly in the Arabian Gulf as well as social media (particularly in the Maghreb and North Africa); Microsoft Teams and Blackboard are exploited sometimes, while Moodle and Edmodo are rarely utilized. DOL technologies have implications for the educational process such as diversifying learning strategies, updating course materials content, enhancing interaction, and designing an online lecture with DOL technologies in mind. However, neutral feedback was shown about whether or not research-based assignments, learner-centered educational content, and continuous formative assessment of all CLOs were systematically adopted.</i></p>

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has pushed the world's educational institutions towards sudden changes; while some countries were technically and logistically prepared, others were not, due to the gap existing between countries that adopt information and communication technology (ICT), and those that are unable to integrate it into their educational establishments.

The current research deals with universities in the Arab region to measure their capacity in terms of technological infrastructure and the efficiency of professors in information and communication technology. At the same time, the research will address the repercussions of using modern technologies on the educational process, especially in the Colleges of Media and Communication in the region.

Literature Review

Concept of Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Among the definitions that have traditionally dealt with the concept of information and communication technology is the one stated by the United Nations since 1999, which explains that information and communication technology includes Internet services, telecommunications equipment and services, information technology equipment and services, media, and broadcasting, libraries, documentation centers, business information providers, network-based information services and other related information and communication activities (Noor-ul-Amin, 2013). Other definitions came to explore the concept; Melissa and others (2007) considered that information and communication technology is one of the forms of technology that can be used in the processes of creating, processing, storing, transmitting, displaying, and exchanging information by various technical means. Thus, this technology includes not only traditional technical tools such as radio and television but also modern devices like mobile phones, computers, networks, software, satellite systems, and

other modern means and technologies, as well as services and associated applications such as video conferencing and blogging.

These technologies represent a golden opportunity for educators to invest in teaching and learning, and the need for their use has grown even more urgent with the onset of the global COVID-19 pandemic.

ICT in the Education sector

It is worth noting that distance online education began years before the outbreak of the pandemic, and since its appearance, it has become the subject of wide-ranging research, particularly to address its features as well as to measure its impact on the educational system. Salama (2010) Stressed the need to integrate ICT into Higher education; his findings showed that the use of ICT was motivating, engaging, and able to empower students' communication skills. Ahmadi et. Al. (2011) conducted a quantitative study to explore the role of student's perceptions of the online learning process; the authors noted that psychological factors play a major role in the proficiency of technology and the success of online education. Nomass(2013)addressed the impact of the use of technology on teaching the English language; she focused on the learner experience through a case study of a typical English classroom wherein the students' experiences were closely monitored to deduce the drawbacks of more traditional methods while also pointing out possible remedies.

Snoussi (2019a) explored the experience of using ICTs in the Emirate universities; the result showed that the studied sample was facing challenges of the transformation of the curriculum, mainly in humanities and social sciences; the author expanded her research focusing on the learning management systems (LMS) usage in private universities located in Dubai, to address the opportunities offered by these technological tools, and the challenges university professors face while using them (Snoussi, 2019b); the 54 interviewees participating in the study mentioned opportunities related to organizing and delivering online lectures and assessments, accessibility of handouts, and interactivity; some challenges were also cited, such as the lack of students' self-discipline in the online environment, the discrepancy of the LMS with programs delivered in the Arabic language, and the technical illiteracy.

Distance Online Learning

The Concept of Distance Learning appeared along with the technology-based learning approaches; it is linked to the accessibility of learning resources anytime and anywhere; It is distinct as a method of learning remotely without being in regular face-to-face contact with a teacher in the classroom (Snoussi & Radwan, 2020); this type of education is due originally to Correspondence Learning which was adopted in many universities in the world years ago (Midgley &Resalat, 2020).Whereas correspondence education originally was based on sending paper-books and course materials by mail, the Internet made it easier and opened the way for new settings: deliverance of distance learning synchronously and asynchronously; Distance Online Learning (DOL) appeared then as a solution to several obstacles that prevent a student from physically attending the classroom.

The literature revealed richness research on topics related to Distance Online Learning methods and approaches; Olivier (2002) states that the spread of DOL has led to a paradigm shift in the educational system, which was not limited to the process of changing traditional concepts of learning, but extended to include changes in E-learning environments to improve performance in the areas of teaching and learning (Nawaz and Konde, 2010); this qualitative shift from traditional ICT to modern technologies can be described through three stages: Traditional e-learning, blended learning, and contemporary virtual e-learning. Vaughan et al. (2013) noted the opportunities that new platforms provide for online learners, and encouraged trainers to adopt active learning methods as instructional techniques; they observed that active learning encourages participation, interaction, and student participation but also requires active learning practice.

Yetik et al. (2020) put a special emphasis on the experience of DOL during the Covid-19 pandemic; they exposed the influence of the distance online learning methods in the way communication courses are delivered; the authors established how Web-based course delivery technology represents the best way to teach practical Media lectures such as LMS, Kahoot, Quizlet, Crowdsignal, etc.

To sum up, Research on distance education has developed over the years, while the first studies were devoted to the characteristics of use, the opportunities offered by ICTs, especially distance education tools and techniques, others studied their effects on the educational process, especially in enhancing interaction. Recently published research sheds light on the experiences of distance online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic and the measures taken to adjust learning methods and techniques in the online environment.

This study is dedicated to exploring the implications of using DOL methods in media and communication studies in light of the sudden shift towards distance education called for by the global Covid-19 pandemic; Special emphasis will be placed on universities in the Arab region, where little research has been devoted to them.

Research problem

The central question of the study can be formulated as follows: To what extent are Arab universities prepared to engage in the distance education system during the Coronavirus pandemic, and what is the impact of this experience on the educational process in the faculties of media and communication from the point of view of professors?

Three sub-questions are branched from this central question as follows:

1. What is the level of proficiency of Arab university professors in terms of information and communication technologies?
2. What are the most widely used Distance Online Learning (DOL) platforms in universities in the Arab region?
3. What is the impact of using DOL technologies on the overall educational process of teaching communication and media studies from the instructors' point of view?

Research hypotheses:

H1: There are statistically significant differences at the level of significance α 0.05 between the average response of the professors' answers on all the axes of the study according to the variable of the type of university.

H2: There are statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha \geq 0.05$ between the average response of professors to mastering platforms in DOL, according to the age variable;

H3: There are statistically significant differences at the level of significance α 0.05 between the average response of professors about the impact of the use of DOL operations on the educational process according to geographic area.

Research Method

This descriptive study is based on a survey; the sample size was determined with a confidence level of (0.05) according to the sampling theory.

Sample and sampling

The sample included 575 media and communication professors from the Arab region who responded to an electronic questionnaire designed through Google Forms and distributed via e-mail messages and social media. The questionnaire, distributed in June and July 2021, consists of two parts, the first identifies the demographic data that represent the independent variables, while the second part includes the study axes and quantitative data. After collection and revision from Google Drive, the data were processed, analyzed and statistical results were extracted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences under Windows - SPSSWIN-V23.

Statistical tests used

1. Frequency and percentages;
2. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation;
3. Person Correlation to measures the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables of a category type;
4. T-test for independent samples;
5. One-dimensional analysis of variance: the differences between the arithmetic means of more than two groups;
6. Post Hoc Tests (LSD: Least Significance Difference).

Significance considered in this study was limited to $P < 0.05$, with a confidence score of (95%) or greater. A five-point Likert scale was used; The range $5-1 = 4$ was calculated and the result was divided by the scale cells (i.e. $4/5 = 0.8$), then this value was added to the lowest rate. A Likert scale was also used in the quadrant by calculating the range $4-1 = 3$, and the result was divided by the cells of the scale $3/4 = 0.75$, then this value was added to the lowest rate as well. (see table.1)

Table No. (1) an estimated balance for the five- Likert scale

Five-point Likert Scale			Four-point Likert Scale		
Degree	Response		Weighted average	Response	Weighted average
(5)	strongly agree	Excellent	4.2-5.0		
(4)	Agree	good	3.4-4.2	Always	3.25-4.0
(3)	Undecided	middle	2.6-3.4	Frequently	2.5-3.25
(2)	Disagree	weak	1.8-2.6	Some times	1.75-2.5
(1)	strongly disagree	I don't know	1-1.8	Rarely	1-1.75

Validity and stability measures :

The study tool was applied to a random exploratory sample of (20) individuals. The responses were entered into the statistical program; An aggregate variable was created for each of the study axes phrases, and the relationship between each phrase with the aggregate variable of the same axis was measured using Person Correlation. The statistical relationship at a significant level (0.01), and the stability of the questionnaire was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha (α) to ensure the stability of the study tool and that the answer would be approximately the same if it was repeated, and it was excluded from the total sample as shown in the table number 2.

Table No. (2) shows the internal consistency and stability of the study tool

Axes	Person Correlation	Alpha Cronbach
IT Proficiency Level	0.337**	0.920
Platforms used	0.456**	0.726
The impact of the use of communication and media technologies	0.854**	0.939
Total		0.857

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It is clear from the data in Table No. 2 that all Pearson correlation coefficients are statistically significant at the level of significance (0.01), and the value of the total reliability coefficient (alpha) is (0.857), which is a high degree of stability.

Research findings

Demographic data

According to Table 3, 56% of the participants are male and 44% are female. 30.1% are under 30 years old; The majority majored in journalism (37%), 86% were affiliated with public universities, and 54.8% were in the Arab Gulf region. It should also be noted that 45.9% taught less than five (5) distance courses (using DOL technologies).

Table No. (3): sample composition

Study population profile		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	322	56
	Female	253	44
Age	Less than 30 years	173	30.1
	From 30-40 years	122	21.2
	From 41-50 years	122	21.2
	From 51-60 years	120	20.9
	Above 60 years	38	6.6
Specialization	Journalism	211	36.7
	Public relations	171	29.7
	radio and television	162	28.2
	Other	31	5.4
the University	public/public university	495	86.1
	private university	80	13.9
Nationality	The Arabian Gulf	315	54.8
	North Africa and the Maghreb	221	38.4
	The Arab Levant	39	6.8
Distance	Above than 15	4	0.7
	Between 11-15	101	17.6
	Between 5-10	206	35.8
	Less than 5	264	45.9

ICT's proficiency level of participants

This section is dedicated to answering the first research question (RQ1) about: What is the level of proficiency of Arab university professors in information and communication technology?

The data indicate that the overall mean level of ICT proficiency among Arab university professors of information and communication is 4.02, which reflects good efficiency; participants use both mobile phones and computers for academic purposes excellently, using 4.35 and 4.25; they also report an excellent level of use of Internet resources, by means = 4.25. For projectors, multimedia software, and educational platforms, usage was good with means of 3.99, 3.83, and 3.42, respectively.

Table No. (4): Level of participants' mastery of information and communication technology

Tools		Excellent	Good	Middle	Weak	I don't know	Mean	Std-Deviation	Degree
Mobile	n	222	334	19	0	0	4.35	0.54	Excellent
	%	38.6	58.1	3.3	0	0			
PC	n	229	261	85	0	0	4.25	0.7	Excellent
	%	39.8	45.4	14.8	0	0			
internet	n	228	262	85	0	0	4.25	0.7	Excellent
	%	39.7	45.6	14.8	0	0			
Data Show	n	145	296	116	18	0	3.99	0.76	Good
	%	25.2	51.5	20.2	3.1	0			
Multimedia	n	129	250	164	32	0	3.83	0.84	Good
	%	22.4	43.5	28.5	5.6	0			
platforms	n	48	247	189	82	9	3.42	0.89	Good
	%	8.3	43	32.9	14.3	1.6			
General Mean							4.02	0.63	Good

According to the survey' findings, there are some significant differences between the average response of professors to mastering information and communication technologies, especially DOL technologies, according to the geographic area: Although Figure (1) shows that skill levels and uses are close among participants in different geographical areas, differences are observed Minor: Participants from the Maghreb and North African countries are the most distinguished as smart mobile phone users with a mean = 4.39, while those in the Arab Gulf universities excel in using computers, the Internet resources and in manipulating multimedia tools with means = 4.26, 4.27 and 3.84, respectively. As for the universities of the Arab Levant, the use of projectors is the best with an average = 4.03.

Thus, to answer the RQ1, it is important to emphasize that the overall mean level of ICT proficiency reflects a good level, but some differences are noted in terms of the technical tools used, according to the geographical area; while professors from the Maghreb and North Africa use more smartphones, those from the Arab Gulf area are more computer manipulators and make more use of internet resources; Arab Levant universities rely more on data projectors.

figure No. (1): The average level of ICT proficiency according to the geographical area

Platforms used for Distance Online Learning

To address the research question on the most widely used Distance Online Learning (DOL) platforms in universities of the Arab region (RQ2), a multiple answers' question was designed including eight (8) platforms' names as options, with a 9th column for "other platforms"; a four-point Likert scale was also used (always to rarely), to measure the frequency of use.

According to the survey data, participants seem to be more familiar with the Zoom platform, declaring its use with mean = 3.33 as well as social media (mean = 3.11). Microsoft Teams, Blackboard, and some other platforms are sometimes used by means = 2.21, 2.00, and 1.89 respectively. Moodle, Google Classroom, Open eCourses, and Edmodo platforms are rarely used by means = 1.56, 1.43, 1.29, and 1.22 respectively. It should be noted that the overall average use of educational platforms is 2.22, that is, there is generally moderate use of educational platforms among the sample.

Table No. (5): Platforms used in the DOL operations

Platforms		Always	Frequently	Some time	Rarely	Mean	Std-Deviation	Use
Zoom	n	237	289	49	0	3.33	0.63	Always
	%	41.2	50.3	8.5	0			
Social Media	n	244	224	36	71	3.11	0.98	Always
	%	42.4	39	6.3	12.3			
Microsoft Teams	n	22	167	298	88	2.21	0.74	Some time
	%	3.8	29	51.8	15.3			
Blackboard	n	49	133	162	231	2	0.99	Some time
	%	8.5	23.1	28.2	40.2			
Model	n	0	92	137	346	1.56	0.75	Rarely
	%	0	16	23.8	60.2			
ClassRoom	n	6	23	185	361	1.43	0.62	Rarely
	%	1	4	32.2	62.8			
Online Course	n	0	22	125	428	1.29	0.53	Rarely
	%	0	3.8	21.7	74.4			
Edmodo	n	30	4	26	515	1.22	0.7	Rarely
	%	5.2	0.7	4.5	89.6			
Other Platforms	n	13	113	248	201	1.89	0.79	Some time
	%	2.3	19.7	43.1	35			
General Mean						2.22	0.62	Some time

In the meantime, there are some significant differences between the averages responses in terms of platforms used for distance online learning, by geographic affiliation. Participants working in the Arab Gulf always use Zoom with a mean = 3.56, while participants in North African and Maghreb universities use Social Networks with a mean = 3.19; Microsoft Times, Blackboard, Open Online Courses, and other learning platforms were the platforms sometimes used in both the Arab Gulf and North African and Maghreb countries with significant differences (mean = 2.22, 3.2, 1.95 and 1.96), while Moodle and Edmodo are rarely used in the Arab Levant (means = 1.65 and 1.53).

Figure No (2): The mean level of platforms used according to the geographic area

To answer RQ2, the results revealed that participants affiliated with the Arab region's universities use the Zoom the most; the platform is always used in the Arabian Gulf. Social media has also been adopted as an educational tool, particularly in the Maghreb and North Africa; Microsoft Teams and Blackboard are sometimes used primarily in both fields while Moodle and Edmodo are rarely used in all universities in the region, including the Arab Levant.

Implications for the use of DOL in colleges of Media and Communication

To investigate the implications for the use of DOL in colleges of Media and Communication from the professors' point of view (RQ3); a multiple answers question was designed including 15 statements to give participants a variety of choices to answer the question; a five-point Likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree) was also comprised to accurately identify views.

Data show that the respondents agreed that the use of DOL technologies affects the educational process (mean = 3.65); participants strongly agree that they have become more careful about evaluating students fairly, using more than one teaching strategy to deliver courses (mean = 4.40 and 4.34). They also confirmed that they are now more insistent on updating and organizing the lecture content, interactively providing the learning process, mastering Learning Management Systems (LMS) in a better way, and designing the online course with DOL technologies in mind (means = 4.11, 4.09, 3.91, 3.71, 3.57, 3.53, 3.42).

Meanwhile, participants remained neutral about whether they consistently push students into teamwork and deep research to find answers, design educational content in a learner-centered manner, respond to students' queries, provide them with immediate feedback, diversify assessment tools, and adopt continuous formative assessment for all CLO's (means= 3.39, 3.34, 3.33, 3.32, 3.31, 3.01).

Table No. (6): The implications for using DOL in colleges of Media and Communication

Statements		strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	strongly disagree	Mean	Std-Deviation	Instagram																																																																																																																																																																																																																																						
Ensure that students are evaluated objectively and fairly	N	318	197	34	26	0	4.4	0.79	strongly agree																																																																																																																																																																																																																																						
	N	55.3	34.3	5.9	4.5	0				I am keen to use more than one means to deliver information	N	307	175	80	8	5	4.34	0.83	strongly agree	N	53.4	30.4	13.9	1.4	0.9	I became keener to update the scientific material of my courses continuously	N	228	232	72	34	9	4.11	0.94	Agree	N	39.7	40.3	12.5	5.9	1.6	The use of information technology helped me to organize the content of the lessons more	N	218	253	44	60	0	4.09	0.93	Agree	N	37.9	44	7.7	10.4	0	I have chosen the appropriate e-learning tools that increase the effectiveness of the learning process and serve its objectives.	N	162	259	97	52	5	3.91	0.94	Agree	N	28.2	45	16.9	9	0.9	Ensure that the learners are involved in the learning process interactively	N	95	278	157	33	12	3.71	0.88	Agree	N	16.5	48.3	27.3	5.7	2.1	Using information technology has helped me deal with learning management systems effectively	N	141	168	158	93	15	3.57	1.1	Agree	N	24.5	29.2	27.5	16.2	2.6	Using information technology helped me master the basic skills of distance e-learning	N	139	179	113	137	7	3.53	1.13	Agree	N	24.2	31.1	19.7	23.8	1.2	I try to take into account the differences between the characteristics of students while designing the course, to provide an educational experience that takes into account the needs and characteristics of the learners.	N	102	172	178	110	13	3.42	1.06	Agree	N	17.7	29.9	31	19.1	2.3	Use a learning strategy that encourages interaction and teamwork	N	129	149	136	137	24	3.39	1.19	Undecided	N	22.4	25.9	23.7	23.8	4.2	I now use the question strategy and encourage students to search for answers	N	102	145	200	103	25	3.34	1.1	Undecided	N	17.7	25.2	34.8	17.9	4.3	I redesign the content of my lessons in a learner-centered way	N	110	115	218	119	13	3.33	1.07	Undecided	N	19.1	20	37.9	20.7	2.3	I became keener to communicate with my students by responding to students' inquiries and providing them with immediate feedback	N	119	140	142	156	18	3.32	1.17	Undecided	N	20.7	24.3	24.7	27.1	3.1	I am keen to diversify the assessment methods between tests, assignments, projects, discussions, and other various assessment methods	N	149	130	80	183	33	3.31	1.31	Undecided	N	25.9	22.6	13.9	31.8	5.7	Use continuous formative evaluation for all lesson objectives to ensure the quality of course outcomes	N	78	123	137	198	39	3.01	1.17	Undecided	N	13.6	21.4	23.8	34.4	6.8	General Mean					
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	N	53.4	30.4	13.9	1.4	0.9				I became keener to update the scientific material of my courses continuously	N	228	232	72	34	9	4.11	0.94	Agree	N	39.7	40.3	12.5	5.9	1.6	The use of information technology helped me to organize the content of the lessons more	N	218	253	44	60	0	4.09	0.93	Agree	N	37.9	44	7.7	10.4	0	I have chosen the appropriate e-learning tools that increase the effectiveness of the learning process and serve its objectives.	N	162	259	97	52	5	3.91	0.94	Agree	N	28.2	45	16.9	9	0.9	Ensure that the learners are involved in the learning process interactively	N	95	278	157	33	12	3.71	0.88	Agree	N	16.5	48.3	27.3	5.7	2.1	Using information technology has helped me deal with learning management systems effectively	N	141	168	158	93	15	3.57	1.1	Agree	N	24.5	29.2	27.5	16.2	2.6	Using information technology helped me master the basic skills of distance e-learning	N	139	179	113	137	7	3.53	1.13	Agree	N	24.2	31.1	19.7	23.8	1.2	I try to take into account the differences between the characteristics of students while designing the course, to provide an educational experience that takes into account the needs and characteristics of the learners.	N	102	172	178	110	13	3.42	1.06	Agree	N	17.7	29.9	31	19.1	2.3	Use a learning strategy that encourages interaction and teamwork	N	129	149	136	137	24	3.39	1.19	Undecided	N	22.4	25.9	23.7	23.8	4.2	I now use the question strategy and encourage students to search for answers	N	102	145	200	103	25	3.34	1.1	Undecided	N	17.7	25.2	34.8	17.9	4.3	I redesign the content of my lessons in a learner-centered way	N	110	115	218	119	13	3.33	1.07	Undecided	N	19.1	20	37.9	20.7	2.3	I became keener to communicate with my students by responding to students' inquiries and providing them with immediate feedback	N	119	140	142	156	18	3.32	1.17	Undecided	N	20.7	24.3	24.7	27.1	3.1	I am keen to diversify the assessment methods between tests, assignments, projects, discussions, and other various assessment methods	N	149	130	80	183	33	3.31	1.31	Undecided	N	25.9	22.6	13.9	31.8	5.7	Use continuous formative evaluation for all lesson objectives to ensure the quality of course outcomes	N	78	123	137	198	39	3.01	1.17	Undecided	N	13.6	21.4	23.8	34.4	6.8	General Mean							3.65	0.78	Agree												
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So, to answer RQ3, the data revealed that the use of DOL technologies affects the educational process; Participants strongly agree that they are becoming more careful during student assessments, diversifying learning strategies during their lectures, updating lecture content and organization, interactively providing the learning process, better mastering Learning Management Systems (LMS) and designing the online course with DOL technologies in mind. However, neutral feedback was shown about whether participants push students into an active environment more suitable for the online setting, where a collaborative spirit is encouraged as well as

deeply research-based assignments, learner-centered educational content and continuous formative assessment for all CLOs.

Test of Research hypotheses

H1: *There are statistically significant differences at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ between the average response of the professors' answers on all the axes of the study according to the variable of the type of university.*

Statistically significant differences were noted between the averages of public universities versus private universities in favor of public universities (mean = 4.05 and 3.81) in terms of professors' proficiency and the use of ICT (T = 3.149). Besides, statistically significant differences were found between these two types of universities in terms of the impact of the use of DOL techniques on Media and Communication studies in favor of the public sector (mean = 3.69 and 3.45), where the T value was 2.223. It should also be noted that in both cases, the differences are significant at a level less than (0.05).

Table No. (7): T-test between the average axes of the study according to the variable of the type of university

Axis	University	Mean	Std-Deviation	T	Sig
mastery of use	governmental university	4.05	0.6	3.149**	0.002
	private university	3.81	0.78		
the influence	governmental university	3.69	0.75	3.223**	0.001
	private university	3.45	0.87		

H2: *There are statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha \geq 0.05$ between the average response of professors to mastering platforms in DOL, according to the age variable.*

The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the average proficiency and use of DOL platforms by age group in favor of the fewer than 30 years old group (P = 5.667), and it was statistically significant at a level less than (0.05). To find out the differences, the subsequent tests were used as shown in table 8 as follows:

Table No. (8): The differences between the average platforms uses in DOL according to the age

Age	Mean	Std-Deviation	F	Sig
Less than 30 years	2.42	0.72	5.667**	0
From 30-40 years	2.25	0.7		
From 41-50 years	2.21	0.63		
From 51-60 years	2.17	0.66		
Above 60 years	2.09	0.54		

H3: *There are statistically significant differences at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ between the average response of professors about the impact of the use of DOL operations on the educational process according to geographic area.*

The data indicate that there are statistically significant differences between the average impact of the use of information and communication technology in the educational process during teaching media and communication studies in Arab universities by geographical region, as the value of P = 49.396 is statistically significant at a level of less than 0.05 in favor of the Arab Gulf countries.

Table No. (9): The differences between the averages in the impact of the ICT's use in the educational process according to the variable of the geographical area

Geographical area	Mean	Std-Deviation	F	Sig
North Africa and the Maghreb	3.97	0.78	49.396**	0
Arabian Gulf	3.43	0.85		
Arab Levant	3.47	0.68		

Discussions and Conclusion

Findings designate a good level of ICT proficiency, but some differences are noted in terms of the technical tools used according to the geographical area; while professors from the Maghreb and North Africa use more smartphones, those from the Arab Gulf area are more computer manipulators and make more use of internet resources; Arab Levant universities rely more on data projectors. This demand for the use of modern

technologies in education is consistent with what was found in previous studies; Salama (2010) for example showed that the use of ICT was motivating, engaging, and able to empower students' communication skills. Respondents use the Zoom platform the most in the Arab region, mainly in the Arabian Gulf. Social media has also been adopted as an educational tool, particularly in the Maghreb and North Africa; Microsoft Teams and Blackboard are sometimes used while Moodle and Edmodo are rarely exploited in all universities of the region. These results are in line with those of Yetik et al. (2020) who addressed the implications of DOL methods on the way communication courses are delivered and concluded that online course delivery technology represented the best way to teach media and communication lectures; they argued that LMS platforms, as well as online games, represent an attractive way to take regular lectures and short review.

As for the differences in terms of the technological tools used, the authors believe this situation is due to the capabilities owned by each party. While there are high potentials in the Gulf countries to acquire computers and pay to use LMS platforms like BlackBoard, the professors of the Maghreb and some countries of the Arab Levant resort to using smartphones in the absence of a strong technological infrastructure. This statement has already been mentioned in previous research findings (Snoussi et al., 2021), where the authors note a gap between Arab countries regarding the ownership and use of educational technologies; the Gulf region has witnessed high-level infrastructure and technical facilities that enable universities to adapt quickly and smoothly to the requirements of distance education, while other Arab countries still suffer from a weak communication network and a lack of financial resources that prevented the possession of a sufficient number of computers and advanced educational software.

In the meantime, data revealed that the use of DOL technologies affects the educational process; participants strongly agree that they are becoming more careful during student assessments, diversifying learning strategies during their lectures, updating lecture content and organization, interactively providing the learning process, better mastering Learning Management Systems (LMS) and designing the online lecture with DOL technologies in mind. This is reminiscent of the findings of Vaughan et al. (2013) where they stated the opportunities offered by new platforms to online learners, mainly the cooperative work enhancement.

However, neutral feedback was shown about whether participants (university professors) push students into deeply research-based assignments, learner-centered educational content, and continuous formative assessment for all CLOs; it seems that the mentioned attitude hides a hesitation about the efficiency of the distance education process; the same pretentiousness was found in a previous paper, where authors noted a cautious and sometimes skeptical view of the effectiveness of DOL use in Media and Communication courses (Snoussi et al., 2021).

In conclusion, it must be emphasized that the transformation imposed by the global Covid-19 pandemic, two years ago, has affected the learning process and led to an irreversible development in the education system. It seems that blended learning will become popular all over the world in the coming years considering the effects that have taken place in terms of curricula as well as a new teaching, learning, and assessment methods that suit the online environment; this will be the focus of our research in the coming period, as the maturity of the hybrid education experience in the Arab region will be addressed.

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